

GO-FORWARD

GEOTHERMAL EXPLORATION AND **O**PTIMIZATION THROUGH
FORWARD MODELING AND RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT

D2.1: ML-based techniques for enriching databases

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List of Abbreviations

CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
RF	Random Forest
SVR	Support Vector Regression
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting Machine Learning
ML	Machine Learning
GR	Gamma Ray log
RHOB	Density log
DT	Sonic log
NPHI	Neutron Density log
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
BSE	Back Scattered Electron
CL	Cathodoluminescence
MM	Mineral Map
RBF	Radial Basis Function
IoU	Intersection over Union
SLIC	Simple Linear Iterative Clustering

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) methods and trained models developed in Task 2.1 of Work package 2 of the Horizon Europe project GO-Forward during the first 21 months of the project. The objective of Task 2.1 is to develop ML-based techniques for providing calibration data for sedimentary-, diagenetic- and fracture-forward-modeling approaches. The calibration data, such as facies, seismic horizons, porosity or mineral phases is derived from primary datasets, e.g. seismic data, well-log data, image data (thin section or SEM data). The methods are to be used in the subsequent forward modeling workflows employed in Work package 3. Three distinct data domains are addressed in this deliverable: seismic data, scanning electron microscope (SEM) image data, and well-log / core-plug data.

- **Seismic data:** Self-supervised and semi-supervised deep learning methods were applied for data conditioning (denoising and interpolation of vintage seismic data) and automated interpretation (fault detection and horizon classification). These methods directly support geothermal exploration by enabling efficient processing of large volumes of legacy 2D and 3D seismic data.
- **SEM image data:** A two-stage image segmentation pipeline combining Random Forest classification and U-Net deep learning was developed for automated mineral phase identification in sandstone thin sections. The pipeline distinguishes pore space, primary quartz, quartz overgrowth, and other mineral phases from paired BSE and CL images. This provides quantitative input for diagenetic forward modeling of clastic reservoirs. The pipeline supports pseudo-labeling and iterative self-training to maximize performance with limited labelled data.
- **Well-log data:** Supervised ML regression models were trained on a compiled dataset of nine wells from the Netherlands (NLOG database) to predict core plug porosity from well-log measurements. After systematic core-log depth alignment and feature engineering, five ML algorithms were compared. Support Vector Regression (SVR) achieved the best performance, demonstrating the feasibility of ML-based porosity prediction as calibration input for stratigraphic forward models.

All trained models, usage documentation, and associated datasets are published as open-access resources on Zenodo (see section 1.3) under EUPL-1.2 (code) with appropriate data provenance documentation.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this document

This document accompanies the published machine learning models (ML-models) developed in Task 2.1 over the course of the first 21 Months of the EU-project GO-Forward. For developing ML-models, three different data sources were used:

1. Seismic data
2. SEM image data
3. Well-log data

Different ML-algorithms were applied to the respective datasets to train ML-models. The following chapters focus on the respective datasets and briefly describe the algorithms used for each one, the architecture of the codebase and how the published machine learning models can be used.

1.2 Note on deliverable scope and realization

The original description includes automatic fracture identification in BHI, LIDAR and photogrammetry data. Due to insufficient labelled fracture image data during the development of the image classification methods, this component was replaced with a rich SEM image dataset, provided by GEUS. The replacement dataset has direct significance for diagenetic forward modeling of clastic reservoirs in GO-Forward. The underlying methodology (CNN-based image segmentation and edge detection) is directly transferable to fracture identification, given that sufficient training data becomes available. As of now (31.05.2026), the fracture identification is not included but will be further extended to labelled fracture image data, if labelled data from GO-Forward field excursions from 2025 will become available. Note that seismic-scale fault identification has been addressed in chapter 2.

1.3 Data availability

Trained models, workflows, and open datasets for the three data sources are accessible under the following links and data repositories:

Dataset / Codebase	Repository	Description / Link
Well-log data (see Chapter 4)	Zenodo	Published under the GO-Forward community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20428397
Well-log core depth alignment code (see Chapter 4)	Zenodo	Published on zenodo as supplementary of a publication https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.18255487
SEM data (see Chapter 3)		Labeled training data for SEM Dataset used https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/5TWAZK
Trained models SEM - Single stage UNet_best - RF	Zenodo	Published under the GO-Forward community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20442586
Trained Seismic models	Zenodo	Published under the GO-Forward community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20441181
Carbonate thin section images	Zenodo	Published under the GO-Forward community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20425839
Carbonate thin section segmentation code	Zenodo	Published under the GO-Forward community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20425839

2 ML methods for seismic data

Two objectives were targeted with development and application of ML-models to seismic data: (i) AI data conditioning and (ii) AI-supported seismic horizon and fault interpretation. Conditioning of seismic data is a strongly needed development, as geothermal exploration often relies on the usage of older, vintage 2D and 3D seismic data. AI-supported interpretation and detection of important geological features in these datasets directly yields necessary calibration parameters for forward models created in WP3 of the HE-Project GO-Forward.

2.1 Input data

Input data to the AI data conditioning and interpretation methods is in general seismic SEG-Y binary data (see <https://seg.org/Publications/SEG-Technical-Standards/>), specifically post-stack seismic reflection amplitudes. The data formats are listed in Table 1 for details. The approach can be applied equally to time- and depth-domain data. The methods work on input SEG-Y data regardless of their processing history and without need for information about the processing history of seismic data.

2.2 Used Methods

Seismic data conditioning comprises denoising of poststack seismic data using self-supervised learning approaches (“Noise2Void”, Birnie et al., 2021) and data augmentation, i.e. interpolating data outliers and gaps using a Generative Adversarial Network (“MDA-GAN”, Dou et al., 2022a). AI-based fault detection is needed to automate the interpretation of faults in large volumes of vintage 2D and 3D seismic data for geothermal exploration. Image segmentation using the semi-supervised learning network FaultSSL (Dou et al., 2022b; Dou et al., 2023) was applied for fault detection. AI-based horizon interpretation should facilitate the automated interpretation of geological horizons in large volumes of vintage 2D and 3D seismic data for geothermal exploration. Image segmentation based on semi-supervised learning was employed to classify formation units within target horizons using CONSS (Li et al., 2023). The neural network model file formats are in general binary files, see table 2 for details.

2.3 Output data

Output data from the AI data conditioning and interpretation methods is in general seismic SEG-Y binary data, see table 3 for details.

2.4 Codebase architecture

The codebase of the various neural networks used in this Work package 2: Enabling Methods consists in general of modified publicly available codes available on the platform GitHub, using python distributions and package managers like Anaconda, Pixi and Uv. The codes used are referred to via their original publications and in general the architectures of the neural networks are a variation of Convolutional Neural Networks or U-nets (Ronneberger et al., 2015). See table 2 for details.

2.5 Data formats

Table 1: Neural Network input file formats

Neural Network Architecture	Input file format
AI Denoiser Pytorch Noise2Void U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
AI interpolator Pytorch MDA-GAN U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
Log2Log Sklearn XGBoost boosted trees	Log ascii LAS file .las
AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultNet U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy

AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultSSL U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
AI Horizon interpretation Pytorch CONSS CNN	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy

Table 2: Neural Network internal modeling file formats

Neural Network Architecture	Neural Network model file format
AI Denoiser Pytorch Noise2Void U-net	Pytorch binary file .pt
AI interpolator Pytorch MDA-GAN U-net	Pytorch binary file .pt
Log2Log Sklearn XGBoost boosted trees	JSON file .json
AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultNet U-net	Pytorch binary file .pt
AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultSSL U-net	Pytorch binary file .pt
AI Horizon interpretation Pytorch CONSS CNN	Python binary pickle file .pkl

Table 3: Neural Network output file formats

Neural Network Architecture	Output file format
AI Denoiser Pytorch Noise2Void U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
AI interpolator Pytorch MDA-GAN U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
Log2Log Sklearn XGBoost boosted trees	Log ascii LAS file .las
AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultNet U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
AI Fault detection Pytorch FaultSSL U-net	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy
AI Horizon interpretation Pytorch CONSS CNN	Seismic data binary SEG-Y .sgy

3 ML methods for SEM data

SEM image data in context of diagenetic forward modeling is often used for generating a data basis with information about relative proportions and timing of mineral phases, which influence the evolution of, e.g. pore-space with progressing diagenesis. In clastic, sandstone dominated reservoirs, important information about mineral phases can, for instance, be the proportion of primary quartz grains to quartz overgrowth.

3.1 Input data

A large dataset of around 8674 SEM images (4337 backscattered electron – BSE images, 4337 cathodoluminescence – CL images in sets, i.e. there is a small overlap between images) in four batches/datasets (see Table 4 for more information). Further, each dataset includes full coverage of Mineral Maps (MM), a downscaled mask of mineral phases present in an image.

3.2 Methods used

The image segmentation pipeline combines classical machine learning and deep learning in a successive two-stage approach, building on results by Andaru & Sausan (2024). First, a Random Forest (RF) classifier is trained using labels from mineral maps or, as fallback, from a multi-Otsu segmentation of BSE images. The RF uses a comprehensive set of features, such as Gabor filters, edge detectors and local statistical measures, extracted from BSE and CL image data.

The two-stage deep learning architecture consists of a U-Net which is first trained on BSE images to segment pore-space, quartz-region, and other minerals. It does not discriminate between other minerals, so is not able to discern, for instance, feldspar from calcite. The quartz-regions in images are then used as a mask on CL-images to train a U-Net on only quartz-regions of CL-images and ultimately

distinguish primary quartz from overgrowth. The employed deep-learning architecture allows for different options to run the segmentation pipeline:

1. Generation of pseudo-labels: For improving the baseline of labeled data, pseudo-labels can be generated using the trained RF model. The user can specify accuracy thresholds for each class to determine when a pseudo-label should be generated from training data.
2. Iterative self-training: This mode extends the pseudo-labeling approach by repeatedly refining trained labels. After the initial U-Net is trained using pseudo-labels, the model is used to predict new labels on the training set. High-confidence predictions are then incorporated as updated pseudo-labels, and the U-Net is retrained. This process is repeated for several iterations, each time using the improved model to generate better pseudo-labels.

All models are evaluated using accuracy, mean IoU (Intersection over Union), and per-class IoU. IoU is an evaluation metric used for evaluating the accuracy in segmentation models by measuring the overlap between predicted mask and ground truth. The model aims at generalisation by including methods for data augmentation and pre- / post-processing methods.

3.3 Codebase architecture

The codebase of the SEM segmentation pipeline is modular and provides opportunities for starting the pipeline at different entry points with a checkpoint system. The main pipeline orchestrates the workflow, calling into modules for data loading, preprocessing, feature extraction, model training (with options for generating pseudo-labels and iterative self-training) and evaluation. The U-Net implementation is based on pyTorch. The pipeline and dataflow is visualized in Figure 1. Configuration of the pipeline, such as path specifications, training-mode choice, activation or deactivation of optional steps is handled via a single Config object.

3.4 Data formats

Table 4: Input files and formats - Image recognition

Input file	File format
Dataset 1 (1017 sets of BSE, CL, MM images)	Tif
Dataset 2 (2046 sets of BSE, CL, MM images)	Tif
Dataset 3 (569 sets of BSE, CL, MM images)	Tif
Dataset 4 (705 sets of BSE, CL, MM images)	Tif
200 labeled images from Dataset 1	JSON

A detailed description of the SEM dataset can be found in the original dataset repository under: <https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/5TWAZK>.

Figure 1 Flow chart depicting the SEM segmentation codebase.

Table 5: Output files and formats - Image recognition

Output file	File format	Description
Pseudo-labels generated by RF	.npz	NumPy compressed archive for storing multiple arrays in a single file.
RF model	.joblib	Serialized Python object using joblib compression. Stores trained scikit-learn RandomForestClassifier.
U-Net models <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single stage UNet_best - Two stage each BSE and CL 	.pth	PyTorch checkpoint file containing model weights, training history, and metadata.
Evaluation metrics	JSON	Human-readable ascii format in JSON structure containing evaluation metrics.
Segmented example images	PNG	Lossless compressed raster image format with segmented example images.

4 ML methods for Well-Log Data

For predicting reservoir parameters from well logs as calibration data for subsequent stratigraphic and diagenetic forward modeling (focus on clastic reservoir modeling workflow) supervised machine learning algorithms were applied to a comprehensive well-log dataset from the Netherlands, compiled from the NLOG database¹. In addition, porosity measurements on core data were provided for nine wells in the database. Consequently, ML methods were focused on regression tasks of porosity for this subset of wells. The results of this work are contained within this deliverable. Transfer of these results to wells in the region without core data is the next step, but beyond the focus of this part of Task 2.1.

4.1 Input data

The target variable was core plug porosity (%), which was upscaled to the log sampling depth using Gaussian kernel convolution. The whole database was filtered using the following requirements: The well had to penetrate the Nieuwerkerk Formation; need to have core plug porosity data; have an acceptable sampling continuity of core plug measurements; and have depth-indexed well log data at the same depth intervals. The input dataset passing this filter comprises nine wells from the West Netherlands Basin and Broad Fourteens Basin, yielding 1787 depth-indexed data points. Train and validation split was 8 / 1, totaling 1602 training samples vs 185 validation samples.

Table 6: Input data from well-log data.

Well-log	Description	Unit
GR (Gamma Ray)	Natural radioactivity; lithological indicator	API
RHOB (Bulk Density)	Bulk density of formation	g/cm ³
DT (Sonic Transit Time)	Compressional wave travel time	µs/ft
NPHI (Neutron Porosity)	Water / Hydrogen-index-based porosity estimation	fraction

¹ <https://www.nlog.nl/en> - last accessed May 2026

4.2 Methods used

A key challenge for porosity estimation from well logs with plug measurements as true baseline data is a correct depth alignment between well-logs and core plug porosity measurements. Multiple methods were combined to a workflow for achieving a sufficient core-log alignment and usability for ML algorithms:

1. Core-log depth alignment – a manual chunk-based alignment was performed as a baseline with core data split into chunks with inter-sample gaps > 3 m.
2. Porosity upscaling – Gaussian kernel convolution was used to reconcile plug-scale (~2-6 cm) porosity with log-scale (~0.3 m) vertical resolution.
3. Feature scaling – using a RobustScaler² for scale-sensitive models, such as Ridge, Elastic Net or SVR
4. Target transformation – A Yeo-Johnson transformation³(Weisberg, 2001) was applied, predictions were back-transformed before evaluation.

The ML algorithms used and compared for porosity regression are; Ridge regression, Elastic Net, SVR (with an RBF Kernel), Random Forest, XGBoost. Validation was performed using a grouped 5-fold cross-validation with wells as groups and one external blind test well. A grid search with this validation strategy was used for hyperparameter tuning, which were evaluated by their mean CV R² (max) and mean CV RMSE (min). SVR performed best with mean CV R² = 0.69, RMSE = 3.85; blind test R² = 0.71, RMSE = 2.38.

4.3 Codebase architecture

The pipeline is implemented in Python using Jupyter Notebooks. The code is published as supplementary material of a publication under DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/18255487>.

4.4 Data formats

Table 7: Input files and formats – Well-Log porosity regression

Input file	File format
Core plug porosity	csv
Core plug grain density	csv
Log (GR, RHOB, DT, NPHI)	Las / csv

Table 8: Output files and formats – Well-Log porosity regression

Output file	File format
Depth aligned Core-Plug / Log pairs	csv
Evaluation metrics	plain-text

² <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.RobustScaler.html> retrieved 27.05.2026

³ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.preprocessing.PowerTransformer.html> retrieved 27.05.2026

5 ML methods for thin sections

Thin section data for classification of mineral phases and porosity, which are relevant calibration parameters for stratigraphic- and diagenetic forward modeling of carbonate systems, were used as input data in unsupervised machine learning algorithms for image segmentation.

5.1 Input data

The input dataset consists of 20 thin section images (1600 x 1200 resolution) of carbonate rock samples with blue-dyed pore space (epoxy), in JPEG format. A strong color contrast between pore space and mineral phases enables automated image segmentation in color space. The images were provided by Fraunhofer IEG as part of the GO-Forward project.

5.2 Methods used

The thin section segmentation pipeline follows a two-step unsupervised workflow:

1. Superpixel segmentation using Simple Linear Iterative Clustering (SLIC): Each image was segmented into superpixels using SLIC. Spatially contiguous pixels with similar color characteristics are grouped into regions (superpixels), reducing the number of pixels from millions of pixels to a couple of thousand homogeneous segments.
2. Color-based clustering: From each superpixel, the mean color features are extracted in LAB (L^* , a^* , b^*) color space, together with the mean grayscale intensity. Features from all images are pooled and clustered into three classes globally using unsupervised algorithms such as K-Means or Gaussian Mixture Models.
 - a. Porespace – identified by the most negative $a^* + b^*$ color signature (typical for blue epoxy color)
 - b. Primary micrite – darker mineral matrix (lower L^* values)
 - c. Diagenetic cement – brighter crystalline phases (higher L^* values)

For extended classification tasks, Haralick texture features (contrast, dissimilarity, ASM, correlation) can be extracted per superpixel.

5.3 Codebase architecture

The processing pipeline is implemented as a single python script with a CLI (command-line interface). The code is structured following the data flow from image loading, superpixel segmentation, feature extraction and calculation of relative proportions, see Figure 2: Flowchart depicting data flow through thin section segmentation..

Carbonate Thin Section Segmentation Pipeline

Figure 2: Flowchart depicting data flow through thin section segmentation.

5.4 Data formats

Table 9: Input files and formats – thin section segmentation

Input file	File format
Input images	JPEG

Table 10: Output files and formats – thin section segmentation

Output file	File format	Description
Phase_fractions	csv	Per image results of phase fractions
Processing parameters	JSON	All processing parameters (n_clusters, method, ...) for reproducibility
Overlay images	PNG	Original image with semi-transparent color overlay

6 References

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